

Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on international research collaboration: Identification of the most critical construct

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Abstract

While the COVID-19 pandemic had a significant negative impact on the world economy, international research collaborations were disrupted by problems like hiring freezes, stopped lab and fieldwork, delayed research infrastructure, socio-cognitive health effects, and restricted travel. This study aims to identify the most critical constructs with the highest relevance to explain the overall impact of the pandemic on international research collaboration. For this purpose, it uses an online pilot survey conducted at a public land-grant research university in the U.S. The online survey included eleven questions on 5-point Likert scales, designed under four constructs, to rate the impact of the pandemic on international research collaboration and its indicators. Thirty-one multilingual/multicultural professors, post-docs, and research assistant Ph.D. students from different departments completed the survey. The findings of this study indicate that resiliency is the most important driver construct for the overall impact of the pandemic on international research collaboration. In other words, consideration of the impact of changes and interventions explored because of COVID-19 on project logistics, research operations, and overall research quality is the most relevant for managerial actions. The results can help design research programs, particularly those involving international collaboration, to reduce the adverse impacts of such adverse conditions.

Introduction

COVID-19, one of the most significant pandemics of the last 100 years, has already caused catastrophic disruptions at the socio-economic levels. Understanding how this pandemic impacted international collaboration is essential to inform program interventions and foster a more connected and resilient global research community (Bogle, 2020; Lee & Haupt, 2021). While the COVID-19 pandemic had a significant negative impact on the world economy, international research collaborations were disrupted by problems like hiring freezes, stopped lab and fieldwork, delayed research infrastructure, socio-cognitive health effects, and restricted travel (Gewin, 2020; Radecki & Schonfeld, 2020; Recio & Colella, 2020).

Since the early 1990s, developed and developing countries have observed a 10- and 20- times rise in internationally co-authored scientific publications (Gewin, 2020). Nearly a quarter of all scientific publications globally are attributed to international collaborations, generating higher citations and more significant societal impacts across the globe (Gewin, 2020; Lee & Haupt, 2021; Miroudot, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic, however, throttled this momentum (Liu et al., 2020; Miroudot, 2020) through a complete disruption in travel, face-to-face interactions, lab work, fieldwork, hiring, and the flow of international students (Bogle, 2020; Brandon-Jones et al., 2014; Gewin, 2020; Radecki & Schonfeld, 2020; Recio & Colella, 2020). This disruption not just plagued discovery and shared scientific progress, particularly in international research, but also choked the national capacity to keep offering a skilled workforce (Bogle, 2020; Brandon-Jones et al., 2014; Gewin, 2020).

Figure 1 shows the United Nations World Tourism Organization data on the percentage of destinations reporting different travel restrictions from across the globe in 2020 (Buitendijk et al., 2020; Fry et al., 2020; ICC, 2020; NSB, 2020; Sy et al., 2020; UNWTO, 2020c). How the enrollment of international students is compared in 2020 and 2019 is shown in Figure 2

(UNWTO, 2020e). Adverse impacts on international research collaborations ranged from cost overruns, human resource limitations to the shutdown of research facilities that diminished research and training opportunities for underrepresented minorities (Bogle, 2020; Radecki & Schonfeld, 2020; Recio & Colella, 2020). Although international collaborations in developed countries were hit hard, developing countries were impacted the hardest (Bogle, 2020). Global research collaborations are also essential to effectively address the diminished skill shortage in advanced economies such as the United States and the United Kingdom and make shared scientific progress with developing countries (Lee & Haupt, 2021). However, understanding how international collaborations can be made more robust and resilient, particularly to the shocks of a global crisis such as the COVID-19 pandemic, is lacking (Bogle, 2020; Gewin, 2020). Lee and Haupt (2021) warn that very few studies have examined international collaborations during a global crisis. More research must be dedicated to understanding how catastrophic disruptions impact research partnerships.

Changes in how scholars currently perform international research are necessary to manage similar potential conditions in the future (Liu et al., 2020). An integrated understanding of how this pandemic influenced active global research collaborations is integral in identifying research and infrastructure gaps and informing current and future international research programs. This study represents the pilot part of a project through which time-sensitive qualitative and quantitative data from active international research projects were collected and synthesized to explain significant gaps, interventions, and opportunities for international collaboration. More specifically, the findings of this paper are based on a pilot survey conducted before the main study.

This study aims to identify the most critical constructs, among international research collaboration *Robustness*, *Resilience*, and *Sustainability*, with the highest relevance to explain the *Overall Impact* of the pandemic on international research collaboration. Multiple studies from diverse disciplines have defined the terms robustness, resilience, and sustainability differently but tend to agree on key aspects that govern their definitions. Robustness, for instance, is defined as the ability to consistently maintain an original function, operation, or structure during uncertainties and disruptions (UNWTO, 2020a, 2020b, 2020d). In the context of international collaborations, understanding the extent to which partnerships remained functional in keeping the original research plan would be significant in analyzing their robustness. On the other hand, resilience is the ability to return to the original function, operation, or structure within an acceptable time after a massive shock or disturbance (Martel, 2020; UNWTO, 2020a, 2020b, 2020d). While robustness and resilience are operational characteristics, sustainability is a strategic attribute. It is seen as the ability to keep the function, operation, or structure at a certain quality appropriate to strategic goals (UNWTO, 2020d). In international research collaborations, sustainability could mean a project team's ability to maintain quality research within an allocated budget and timeline while keeping the team members safe and healthy.

Figure 1. Travel restrictions around the globe (percentage of destinations)

Figure 2. International student enrollment in 2020 compared to 2019

Table 1. Pilot survey questions

Robustness	Q1-1	Rate the impact of the challenges, conflicts, and limitations caused by COVID-19 on team dynamics
	Q1-2	Rate the impact of the challenges, conflicts, and limitations caused by COVID-19 on project logistics
	Q1-3	Rate the impact of the challenges, conflicts, and limitations caused by COVID-19 on research operations
	Q2	Rate the impact of the challenges, conflicts, and limitations caused by COVID-19 on the research process
	Q3	Rate the impact of the challenges, conflicts, and limitations caused by COVID-19 on the research outcomes
	Q4	Rate the impact of constrained travel and facilities shutdown caused by COVID-19 on the project
Resilience	Q5-1	Rate the impact of changes and interventions explored because of COVID-19 on team dynamics
	Q5-2	Rate the impact of changes and interventions explored because of COVID-19 on project logistics
	Q5-3	Rate the impact of changes and interventions explored because of COVID-19 on research operations
	Q6-1	Rate the effectiveness of changes and interventions explored because of COVID-19 on team dynamics
	Q6-2	Rate the effectiveness of changes and interventions explored because of COVID-19 on project logistics
	Q6-3	Rate the effectiveness of changes and interventions explored because of COVID-19 on research operations
	Q7	Rate the impact of changes and interventions explored because of COVID-19 on overall research quality
Sustainability	Q8-1	Rate the impact of the pandemic on the project budget
	Q8-2	Rate the impact of the pandemic on the schedule
	Q8-3	Rate the impact of the pandemic on the health/safety of the team

	Q9	Rate the usefulness of virtual communication technologies available during the pandemic
	Q10	Rate the impact of time zone differences that must be more seriously considered during pandemic, on the project
Overall Impact	Q11	Rate the overall impact of the pandemic on international research collaboration

Methodology

The pilot survey was conducted at a public land-, sea-, and space-grant research university in the U.S. The websites of several departments were searched for multilingual/multicultural professors, post-docs, and research assistant Ph.D. students. The potential participants were invited to complete the online survey. The online survey included eleven questions on 5-point Likert scales, designed under four constructs, to rate the impact of the pandemic on international research collaboration and its indicators (Table 1). Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) was used to identify the key constructs with the highest relevance to explain the endogenous latent variable in the structural model. Based on the ten times rule, the minimum sample size in a PLS-SEM analysis should be ten times the maximum number of arrowheads pointing at a latent variable anywhere in the PLS path model (Hair Jr et al., 2021). As Figure 3 shows, the maximum number of arrowheads pointing at a latent variable in the path model is three. As a result, the minimum sample size in the PLS-SEM analysis is 30. In this pilot study, 31 participants completed the online survey.

Figure 3. Original PLS path model

Results

Systematic evaluation of PLS-SEM results

PLS-SEM aims to maximize the explained variance, i.e., the R^2 value, of the endogenous latent variable in the PLS path model. For this reason, evaluating the quality of the PLS-SEM measurement and structural models focuses on metrics indicating the model's predictive capabilities. Once the reliability and validity of the constructs have been established, only then are the structural model estimates assessed. Reflective measurement models are evaluated on their internal consistency, reliability, and validity. The measures include composite reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity. The structural model's evaluation involves the model's ability to predict the variance in the dependent variables. Hence, the primary assessment criteria for PLS-SEM results are R^2 values as well as the size and significance of the path coefficients. The f^2 effect sizes, predictive relevance (Q^2), and q^2 effect sizes provide further information about the quality of the PLS path model estimations (Hair Jr et al., 2021).

Evaluation of the reflective measurement models

Assessment of reflective measurement models includes composite reliability to evaluate internal consistency, individual indicator reliability, and average variance extracted (AVE) to assess convergent validity. It also includes discriminant validity, which can be examined using the Fornell-Larcker criterion. The composite reliability ranges from 0 to 1, and higher values denote higher levels of reliability. In exploratory research, composite reliability values between 0.60 and 0.70 are acceptable. Internal consistency reliability is lacking when composite reliability values are less than 0.60 (Hair Jr et al., 2021). The results indicate that the measurement models for *Resiliency* and *Sustainability* lack internal consistency reliability (Table 2).

Table 2. Internal consistency reliability of the measurement models

Construct	Composite Reliability								
	Original Model	After Removing							
		Indicators with outer loadings <0.40	Q ₁₋₂	Q ₅₋₂	Q ₅₋₃	Q ₆₋₁	Q ₇	Q ₈₋₂	Q ₈₋₃
Robustness	0.799732	0.859144	0.860472	0.859144	0.859144	0.859144	0.859144	0.859144	0.859144
Resiliency	0.452846	0.686284	0.686284	0.611600	0.454381	0.817410	0.701894	0.686284	0.686284
Sustainability	0.558862	0.688758	0.688758	0.688758	0.688758	0.688758	0.688758	0.738716	0.629187

Indicator reliability refers to the size of outer loading. At a minimum, the outer loadings of all indicators should be statistically significant. Because a significant outer loading could still be weak, a common rule of thumb is that the standardized outer loadings should be 0.70 or higher. When an outer loading is below 0.70, instead of automatically eliminating the indicator, the effects of item removal on the composite reliability and the construct's content validity should be examined carefully. Generally, indicators with outer loadings between 0.40 and 0.70 should be considered for removal from the scale only when deleting the indicator increases the composite reliability or the AVE above the threshold value (Hair Jr et al., 2021). Indicators with outer loadings below 0.40 should always be eliminated from the construct (Bagozzi et al., 1991; Hair et al., 2011). Table 3 represents the outer loadings and deciding to retain or remove the indicators. After removing the indicators with outer loadings below 0.40, all three measurement models indicated acceptable levels of reliability (Table 2).

AVE is a common measure to establish convergent validity on the construct level. The AVE of each reflectively measured construct should be evaluated. An AVE value of 0.50 or higher indicates that, on average, the construct explains more than half of the variance of its indicators (Hair Jr et al., 2021). As shown in Table 4, in the original model, the AVE values of *Robustness*, *Resiliency*, and *Sustainability* are below the required minimum level of 0.50. Hence, the measures of the three reflective constructs do not have the required levels of convergent validity. Deletion of Q₁₋₂, Q₅₋₂, Q₅₋₃, and Q₇ led to no increase in the composite reliability or the AVE above the threshold value. Hence, these indicators were retained. In addition, the deletion of Q₆₋₁, Q₈₋₂, and Q₈₋₃ increased the composite reliability or the AVE above the threshold value. Therefore, these indicators were removed (Table 2, Table 3, and Table 4). In the modified model (Figure 4), the AVE of *Robustness* and *Resiliency* are 0.553 and 0.601, respectively. Since the AVE of both the reflectively measured constructs is above the required minimum level of 0.50, they have the required levels of convergent validity. In the modified model (Figure 4), *Sustainability* is not a reflective construct because it only has one indicator. Accordingly, there is no need to evaluate its AVE.

Table 3. Indicator reliability and decision on retaining, removing, or examining removal effects

Construct	Indicator	Outer Loading	Primary Decision	Composite Reliability		AVE		Increase above Threshold		Final Decision
				Before Removal	After Removal	Before Removal	After Removal	Composite Reliability	AVE	
Robustness	Q ₁₋₁	-0.069329	remove	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	remove

	Q _{1,2}	0.595209	examine removal effects	0.859144	0.860472	0.552795	0.607060	No	No	retain
	Q _{1,3}	0.844649	retain	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	retain
	Q ₂	0.789065	retain	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	retain
	Q ₃	0.745582	retain	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	retain
	Q ₄	0.701313	retain	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	retain
Resiliency	Q _{5,1}	-0.189285	remove	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	remove
	Q _{5,2}	0.448783	examine removal effects	0.686284	0.611600	0.395564	0.396191	No	No	retain
	Q _{5,3}	0.692819	examine removal effects	0.686284	0.454381	0.395564	0.275352	No	No	retain
	Q _{6,1}	0.461968	examine removal effects	0.686284	0.817410	0.395564	0.600785	Yes	Yes	remove
	Q _{6,2}	0.318032	remove	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	remove
	Q _{6,3}	0.001468	remove	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	remove
	Q ₇	0.450588	examine removal effects	0.686284	0.688758	0.395564	0.447588	No	No	retain
Sustainability	Q _{8,1}	0.200354	remove	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	remove
	Q _{8,2}	0.439205	examine removal effects	0.688758	0.738716	0.447588	0.593444	Yes	Yes	remove
	Q _{8,3}	0.622650	examine removal effects	0.688758	0.629187	0.447588	0.531840	No	Yes	remove
	Q ₉	-0.000617	remove	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	remove
	Q ₁₀	0.876997	retain	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	retain

Table 4. The average variance extracted from the measurement models

Construct	AVE									
	Original Model	After Removing								
		Indicators with outer loadings <0.40	Q _{1,2}	Q _{5,2}	Q _{5,3}	Q _{6,1}	Q ₇	Q _{8,2}	Q _{8,3}	
Robustness	0.457145	0.552795	0.607060	0.552795	0.552795	0.552795	0.552795	0.552795	0.552795	
Resiliency	0.176403	0.395564	0.395564	0.396191	0.275352	0.600785	0.464621	0.395564	0.395564	
Sustainability	0.277972	0.447588	0.447588	0.447588	0.447588	0.447588	0.447588	0.593444	0.531840	

The Fornell-Larcker criterion is an approach to assessing discriminant validity. It compares the square root of the AVE values with the latent variable correlations. Specifically, the square root of each construct's AVE should be greater than its highest correlation with any other construct (Hair Jr et al., 2021). As shown in Table 5, the results suggest that the constructs discriminate well because the square root of the AVE of each reflective construct (*Sustainability* is not a reflective measurement anymore.) is larger than the correlations with the remaining constructs in the model.

Figure 4. Modified PLS path model

Table 5. Fornell-Larcker criterion to assessing discriminant validity

Construct	AVE	$\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$	Highest Correlation with Any Other Construct
Overall Impact	1.000000	1	0.417720
Robustness	0.552795	0.7435	0.665330
Resiliency	0.600785	0.7751	0.665330
Sustainability	1.000000	1	0.394515

Evaluation of the structural model

The structural model represents the underlying structural concepts of the path model. Assessment of the structural model results enables determining the model's capability to predict target construct(s). The structural model assessment procedure includes the following steps (Hair Jr et al., 2021):

- Step I. Assessing structural model for collinearity issues
- Step II. Assessing the significance and relevance of the structural model relationships
- Step III. Assessing the level of R^2
- Step IV. Assessing the f^2 effect size
- Step V. Assessing the predictive relevance Q^2
- Step VI. Assessing the q^2 effect size

Step I. Assessing structural model for collinearity issues

The first step is to examine the structural model for collinearity. The path coefficients might be biased if the estimation involves critical levels of collinearity among the predictor constructs. A related measure of collinearity is the variance inflation factor (VIF), defined as the reciprocal of the tolerance (i.e., $VIF = 1/TOL$). To assess the level of collinearity, researchers should compute the tolerance (TOL). Researchers consider tolerance values below 0.20 (VIF values above 5) in the predictor constructs as critical levels of collinearity. Suppose the tolerance or VIF values indicate a critical level of collinearity. In that case, one should consider eliminating constructs, merging predictors into a single construct, or creating higher-order constructs to treat collinearity problems (Hair Jr et al., 2021). In this study, the authors measured tolerance and VIF values to assess collinearity. In doing so, they examined each set of predictor constructs separately for each subpart of the structural model (Figure 4). As Table 6 represents, the tolerance (VIF) value of each predictor construct is higher than 0.20 (lower than 5). Therefore, collinearity among the predictor constructs is not a critical issue in the structural model. Since *Sustainability* has just one indicator, assessing collinearity did not make sense.

Table 6. Tolerance and VIF value of each predictor construct for assessing collinearity

Construct	Dependent Variable	Independent Variable	Collinearity Statistics	
			Tolerance	VIF
Robustness	Q _{1_2}	Q _{1_3}	.482	2.076
		Q ₂	.556	1.798
		Q ₃	.750	1.333
		Q ₄	.642	1.557
	Q _{1_3}	Q _{1_2}	.686	1.457
		Q ₂	.590	1.695
		Q ₃	.767	1.304
		Q ₄	.712	1.405
	Q ₂	Q _{1_2}	.465	2.149
		Q ₁₋₃	.346	2.887
		Q ₃	.757	1.322
		Q ₄	.640	1.563

	Q ₃	Q ₁₋₂	.452	2.214
		Q ₁₋₃	.324	3.087
		Q ₂	.544	1.837
		Q ₄	.670	1.492
	Q ₄	Q ₁₋₂	.458	2.186
		Q ₁₋₃	.356	2.809
		Q ₂	.545	1.836
		Q ₃	.793	1.261
Resiliency	Q ₅₋₂	Q ₅₋₃	.891	1.122
		Q ₇	.891	1.122
	Q ₅₋₃	Q ₅₋₂	.954	1.048
		Q ₇	.954	1.048
	Q ₇	Q ₅₋₂	.338	2.956
		Q ₅₋₃	.338	2.956

Step II. Assessing the significance and relevance of the structural model relationships

The following issues to examine are the significance and relevance of coefficients. The structural model relationships (i.e., the path coefficients) represent the hypothesized relationships among the constructs. The path coefficients have standardized values approximately between -1 and +1. Estimated path coefficients close to +1 represent strong positive relationships (and vice versa for negative values) that are usually statistically significant (i.e., different from zero in the population). The closer the estimated coefficients are to 0, the weaker the relationships. Very low values close to 0 are usually not significantly different from zero. Testing for significance requires applying the bootstrapping routine and examining bootstrapping confidence intervals. If a confidence interval for an estimated path coefficient does not include zero, the hypothesis that the path equals zero is rejected, and we assume a significant effect. After examining the significance of relationships, it is important to assess the relevance of those significant relationships. The path coefficients in the structural model may be significant, but their size may be very small. If the path coefficient is statistically significant, its value indicates the extent to which the exogenous construct is associated with the endogenous construct. An analysis of the relative importance of relationships is crucial for interpreting the results and drawing conclusions since such small coefficients, even though significant, may not warrant managerial attention. The structural model path coefficients can be interpreted relative to one another. If one path coefficient is larger than another, its effect on the endogenous latent variable is greater. By interpreting the results, researchers can identify the key constructs with the highest relevance to explain the endogenous latent variables in the structural model (Hair Jr et al., 2021).

Looking at the relative importance of the exogenous driver constructs for the *Overall Impact*, one finds that *Resiliency* is the most important, followed by *Robustness*. *Sustainability* has less bearing on *Overall Impact* (Table 7). If a confidence interval for an estimated path coefficient does not include zero, the hypothesis that the path equals zero is rejected, and a significant effect is assumed. Since the confidence interval for the estimated path coefficient for the *Sustainability* construct includes zero (Table 7), it is concluded that the effect of the *Sustainability* construct on the overall impact is insignificant.

Table 7. Assessment of the significance and relevance of coefficients

Construct	Path Coefficient	Sample Mean	Standard Error	T Statistics	CI = sample mean ± t × sample error	
					2.5%	97.5%
Robustness	0.186409	0.210804	0.116941	1.594051	0.024	0.397
Resiliency	0.258743	0.264380	0.118923	2.175727	0.006	0.523
Sustainability	0.149959	0.135911	0.090748	1.652468	-0.014	0.286

Step III. Assessing the level of R^2

Next, the endogenous latent variable's R^2 values (i.e., coefficients of determination) should be examined. The R^2 values represent the amount of explained variance of the endogenous constructs in the structural model. In other words, R^2 represents a measure of in-sample predictive power. A well-developed path model to explain certain key target constructs should deliver sufficiently high R^2 values. The R^2 value ranges from 0 to 1, with higher levels indicating higher levels of predictive accuracy. It is difficult to provide rules of thumb for acceptable R^2 values as this depends on the model complexity and the research discipline (Hair Jr et al., 2021). Falk and Miller (1992) recommended that R^2 values be equal to or greater than 0.10 for the explained variance of a particular endogenous construct to be deemed adequate. Cohen (1988) suggested R^2 values of 0.26, 0.13, or 0.02 for endogenous latent variables can be respectively described as substantial, moderate, or weak. Chin (1998) recommended that R^2 values of 0.67, 0.33, or 0.19 for endogenous latent variables can be assessed as substantial, moderate, or weak, respectively. Hair et al. (2011) & suggested in scholarly research that focuses on marketing issues, R^2 values of 0.75, 0.50, or 0.25 for endogenous latent variables can, as a rough rule of thumb, be respectively described as substantial, moderate or weak.

Further, adding nonsignificant constructs, slightly correlated with the endogenous latent variable, to a structural model will increase the R^2 value. Researchers use the adjusted coefficient of determination (R^2_{adj}) for comparing PLS-SEM results involving models with different numbers of exogenous latent variables (Hair Jr et al., 2021). The bootstrapping routine can test for significant differences between R^2_{adj} values between models with three and two exogenous latent variables. Bootstrapping calculates R^2_{adj} values of 0.135 and 0.146 for models with three and two exogenous latent variables, respectively. In other words, the exclusion of *Sustainability* slightly increases the R^2_{adj} of *Overall Impact* from 0.135 to 0.146. Based on what Cohen (1988) recommended, both models with three and two exogenous latent variables show moderate R^2 values for the endogenous latent variable: 0.22 and 0.20, respectively.

Step IV. Assessing the f^2 effect size

The change in the R^2 value when a specified exogenous construct is omitted from the model can be used to evaluate whether the omitted construct has a substantive impact on the endogenous constructs. This measure is referred to as the f^2 effect size. The f^2 effect size enables analyzing the relevance of constructs in explaining selected endogenous constructs. More specifically, it analyzes how much a predictor construct contributes to the R^2 value of a target construct in the structural model. Results of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 are interpreted as small, medium, and large f^2 effect sizes, respectively (Cohen, 1988). Effect size values of less than 0.02 indicate no effect (Hair Jr et al., 2021).

This study obtained the f^2 effect sizes for all structural model relationships. *Robustness*, *Resiliency*, and *Sustainability* have f^2 effect sizes of 0.021, 0.046, and 0.024 on Overall Impact. Hence, the f^2 effect size of *Robustness*, *Resiliency*, and *Sustainability* on the endogenous latent variable is small. In the modified structural model (Figure 4), the f^2 effect size of *Robustness* and *Resiliency* on *Overall Impact* increases ($f^2=0.050$) and decreases ($f^2=0.036$) in amount, respectively. However, they remain small.

Step V. Assessing the predictive relevance Q^2

In addition to evaluating the magnitude of the R^2 values as a criterion of predictive accuracy, researchers should also examine Stone-Geisser's Q^2 value (Geisser, 1974; Stone, 1974). This measure indicates the model's out-of-sample predictive power or predictive relevance. When a PLS path model exhibits predictive relevance, it accurately predicts data not used in the model estimation. In the structural model, Q^2 values larger than zero for a specific reflective

endogenous latent variable indicate the path model's predictive relevance for a particular dependent construct. The Q^2 value is obtained using the blindfolding procedure for a specified omission distance D . Omission distance D between 5 and 10 should be used. In addition, the omission distance D has to be chosen so that the number of observations used in the model estimation divided by D is not an integer. Q^2 values larger than 0 suggest that the model has predictive relevance for a specific endogenous construct (Hair Jr et al., 2021).

In contrast, values of 0 and below indicate a lack of predictive relevance. Researchers usually apply the blindfolding procedure to endogenous constructs with a reflective measurement model specification and endogenous single-item constructs. The blindfolding procedure is a resampling technique that systematically deletes and predicts every data point of the indicators in the reflective measurement model of endogenous constructs. The prediction error of the path model for reflective target constructs is obtained by comparing the original values with the predictions. The computation of the Q^2 value for assessing predictive relevance uses this prediction error. In accordance with the f^2 effect size for the R^2 values, researchers can also compute the q^2 effect size for the Q^2 values. The q^2 effect size of a selected construct and its relationship to an endogenous construct in the structural model use the same critical values for assessment of the f^2 effect size evaluation (Hair Jr et al., 2021).

This study used the blindfolding procedure to assess the predictive relevance of the path model. The study includes 31 observations. The authors chose an omission distance of $D = 7$. Accordingly, dividing the sample size by D did not yield an integer: $31 \div 7 = 4.429$. The results show that the Q^2 value of the endogenous construct is considerably below zero (i.e., -0.153258), which indicates the model's lack of predictive relevance regarding the endogenous latent variable.

Step VI. Assessing the q^2 effect size

The Q^2 values estimated by the blindfolding procedure represent how well the path model can predict the originally observed values. The effect size q^2 allows for assessing an exogenous construct's contribution to an endogenous latent variable's Q^2 value. As a relative measure of predictive relevance, q^2 values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35, respectively, indicate that an exogenous construct has a small, medium, or large predictive relevance for a specific endogenous construct. The results show that the q^2 effect size for the relationships between *Robustness* and *Overall Impact* and between *Resiliency* and *Overall Impact* can be considered large (Table 8).

Table 8. Exogenous constructs' contribution to endogenous variable's Q^2

Construct		$Q^2=1-SSE/SSO$	$q^2=(Q^2_{included} - Q^2_{excluded}) / (1- Q^2_{included})$	Predictive relevance
Robustness	Included	0.333708	0.325	large
	Excluded	0.117343		
Resiliency	Included	0.045603	-0.302	large
	Excluded	0.333708		

Conclusions

This study aims to identify the key construct(s) among *Robustness*, *Resiliency*, and *Sustainability* with the highest relevance to explain the *Overall Impact* of the pandemic on international research collaboration in the proposed structural model. The results show that all the measurement models, i.e., *Robustness*, *Resiliency*, and *Sustainability*, need modification. In the modified model, the authors removed 17% (1 of 6), 57% (4 of 7), and 80% (4 of 5) of the suggested indicators of *Robustness*, *Resiliency*, and *Sustainability*, respectively. Accordingly, the biggest and smallest changes belonged to *Sustainability* and *Robustness*, respectively.

The results retain the hypotheses that *Robustness* and *Resiliency* reduce the *Overall Impact* of the pandemic on international research collaboration. However, they reject the hypothesis that *Sustainability* reduces the *Overall Impact* of the pandemic on international research collaboration. In other words, the findings indicate that the effect of the *Sustainability* construct on the *Overall Impact* is insignificant. It means that considering time zone differences' impact on the project during the pandemic is the least relevant for managerial actions. The findings also show that the effect of *Resiliency* on the *Overall Impact* is greater than the effect of *Robustness*. In other words, this study identifies *Resiliency* as the key construct with the highest relevance to explain the *Overall Impact* of the pandemic on international research collaboration in the structural model.

Further, the modified model shows moderate in-sample predictive power. In addition, the relevance of *Resiliency* and *Robustness* in explaining the *Overall Impact* is small. The findings also indicate that the model lacks out-of-sample predictive power. In other words, the path model's accuracy in predicting the originally observed values is moderate, while it cannot accurately predict data not used in the model estimation. It means that both *Resiliency* and *Robustness* lack out-of-sample predictive power; however, both show moderate in-sample predictive power. The study also shows that *Resiliency* is the most important driver construct of the *Overall Impact*. In other words, *Resiliency* has the highest priority for performance improvement. Accordingly, consideration of the impact of changes and interventions explored because of COVID-19 on *project logistics*, *research operations*, and *overall research quality* is the most relevant for managerial actions.

The findings of this study inform the design and management of global research collaborations for *Resiliency* and *Robustness* to adverse situations such as those created by the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic. Research results may also help research teams design their research to reduce any adverse impacts of such pandemics. However, it must be noted that (a) participation in this pilot survey was not limited to individuals with active international projects during the pandemic, (b) the study was limited to some departments at a land-, sea-, and space-grant research public university in the U.S., (c) participation was limited to multilingual/multicultural individuals. As a result, the findings are limited to the specific sample used in this pilot study.

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